

Treatment of organic contaminants through an advanced technology heterogeneous photocatalysis : An overview

Himakshi Verma*, Neelakshi Verma and R. C. Meena

Department of Chemistry, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur-342 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : vermahimakshi88@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 08 August 2015, accepted 13 August 2015

Abstract : Heterogeneous photocatalysis is an AOP which has been shown to be an effective means of removing organic pollutants from water streams. Metal oxides and some ion exchange resin used as heterogeneous catalyst. Heterogeneous photocatalysis process is able to replace many customary disinfection methods including ozonation, chlorination which are potentially dangerous and often create biologically harmful by-products. It generates very reactive species such as hydroxyl radical that oxidise a broad range of pollutant quickly and non-selectively. Heterogeneous photocatalysis is a versatile, low cost and environmentally benign treatment technology for a host of pollutants. The efficient and successful application of photocatalysis demands that the pollutant, the catalyst and source of illumination are in close proximity or contact with each other.

Keywords : Photocatalytic oxidation, organic pollutants, semiconductor, heterogeneous photocatalysis, photocatalyst.

Introduction

Catalysis can be thought of as an umbrella term to describe any process in which a substance through intimate interaction with the reactants and through a lower energy pathway accelerates an otherwise thermodynamically favoured but kinetically slow reaction¹. Unique can be found under the umbrella of catalysis including photocatalysis, thermal catalysis, acid-base catalysis, redox catalysis and enzyme catalysis. Photocatalysis in particular has become an increasingly important field and a heavily researched topic by all fields of science, including physicists, chemists and surface scientist and is pursued today to solve an ever widening variety of environmental problem.

The term photocatalysis has been used since the 1920's and broadly define as a photoreaction that is accelerated by the presence of a catalyst. Photocatalysis is the acceleration of a chemical reaction by either by direct irradiation or by the irradiation of the catalyst that in turn lowers the activation energy for the primary reaction to occur. Heterogeneous photocatalysis is also known as photocatalytic oxidation which occurs at the surface of a catalyst².

Heterogeneous photocatalytic conversion often accomplishes either a specific, selective oxidation or a complete oxidative degradation of an organic substrate present. These reactions therefore involve photosensitization that is an indirect photo activation of the heterogeneously dispersed particulate absorber rather than the direct formation of an excited state of the substrate. Photo oxidation is the most numerous class of the known photocatalytic reaction of organic substrates. It is typical that high chemical yields of oxidation products are formed, although sometimes with quantum yields of only few percent or less³.

Every organic function group bearing either a non bonded lone pair of any π -conjugation can be activated toward semiconductor photo catalysed oxidative reactivity either by dehydrogenation, oxygenation or oxidative cleavage. The term photo degradation is usually used to refer to complete oxidation mineralisation i.e. the conversion of organic compounds to CO₂, H₂O, NO₃⁻ or other oxides, halide ions, phosphate etc. Semiconductor photocatalysis can be more appealing than the more conventional chemical oxidation methods because semiconductors are inexpensive, non toxic and capable of extended use without substantial loss of photocatalytic activity. These semiconductor particles recovered by filtra-

tion or centrifugation or when immobilized in a fluidized bed reactor retain much of their native activity after repeated catalytic cycles⁴. For example the complete decomposition of 2-ethoxy ethanol^{5,6} can be efficiently carried out on irradiated TiO₂, while CdS and ZnS are less active under same conditions, although the same products are formed. ZnO is also an efficient catalyst for the photodecomposition of phenol⁷. Halogenated substrates have been decomposed successfully on irradiated semiconductor suspensions⁸. DDT is also degraded on TiO₂ excited by stimulated sunlight⁹.

Many semiconductors used as photocatalyst have been investigated like TiO₂, SrTiO₃, CdS, WO₃, ZnS, FeTiO₃, ZrO₂, V₂O₅, Nb₂O₅, SnO₂, etc.¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Photosensitization permits expansion of the wavelength response of the photocatalyst, a goal which is particularly important when the photocatalysts are to be illuminated with natural sunlight since the chemically stable metal oxides are wide band gap semiconductors whose absorption onsets typically occur in the low energy end of the ultraviolet spectrum. Photosensitization of semiconductors by various dyes, monitored by nanosecond and picosecond flash photolysis¹⁵⁻¹⁷, has provided valuable information on the mechanism of interfacial electron transfer on the semiconductor surface. Metal oxides have found greatest utility in heterogeneous photocatalysis because of their resistance to photocorrosion and wideband-gap. Photocatalytic activity of semiconductors are altered by the variables are surface area (roughness), the state of surface hydration and hydroxylation, surface crystallinity, surface charge caused by an excess of cations or anions on the surface, annealing pretreatment, and the presence of dopants and impurities.

Mechanism of photocatalysis :

The photochemical process occurring upon irradiation of a semiconductor¹⁸⁻²¹. A semiconductor has a band structure roughly characterised as a series of energetically closed space energy levels associated with covalent bonding between composing the crystallite (the valence band) and a second series of spatially diffuse, energetically similar levels lying at higher energy and associated with conduction in the macromolecular crystallite (the conduction band). The magnitude of the fixed energy gap between the electrically populated valence band and the

largely vacant conduction band is called band gap²². The band gap also defines the wave length sensitivity of the semiconductor to irradiation. Photo excitation with light of energy greater than the band gap promotes an electron from the valence band to the conduction, creating an electronic vacancy or hole^{23,24} (h⁺). Hole trapping generates a cation radical and electron trapping generating an anion radical. These radical ions are very reactive and can react among them or other adsorbents and recombine by back electron transfer to form the excited state of one of the reactants or to waste the excitation energy by a non-radiative pathway. They may diffuse from the semiconductor surface and participate in chemical reaction in the bulk solution²⁵.

The pair of photo excited charges that occurs with a particle is called an electron hole pair (EHP). The energy required of a photon to generate an EHP in a photocatalyst can be related to its wavelength by :

$$\lambda \text{ (nm)} \leq 1240/E_g$$

The efficiency of a photocatalyst is measured in terms of number of reactions occurring per photon absorbed which depends on the rate of the generation, fate of migration and energy levels of the photo excited EHPs.

Photo active semiconductor surfaces can attract electron donors and acceptors through both chemical and electrostatic forces including van der Waals forces, induced dipole-dipole interaction, dipole-dipole interaction, hydrogen bonding, outer sphere complexation, ion exchange, surface organic matter partitioning and sorbate hydrophobicity.

Electron hole pair recombination :

Electron hole pair recombination creates a loss in photocatalytic efficiency. The recombination process between the photo excited electron and hole can occur either in the volume of semiconductor particle or on the surface of the particle with a by-product of heat release²⁶. The electron hole pair recombination process itself results when the electron hole recombination time is shorter than the

time it takes for the carrier to diffuse to the surface. Electron hole pair recombination occurs on both a picosecond and nanosecond time scale depending on the semiconductor and its particle size²⁷⁻²⁹. As the size of the particle decreases approaching approximately 10–15 nm, electron hole pair recombination decreases since the diffusing charge carriers can quickly reach the surface of the particle. If the particle size decreases below this optimal particle size leading to quantum size electron hole pair recombination again increases due to the close proximity of the charges³⁰⁻³². Other factors such as substitutional impurities, lattice defects and vacancies which can serve as electron traps near the surface or in the bulk, also affect electron hole pair recombination rates since they provide possible alternative pathways for the photo generated electron to recombines with holes.

Role of photogenerated electrons in photocatalysis :

Semiconductors have a high quantum efficiency its photo induced charges must freely migrate to the surface of the particle so that they can participate in reactions with adsorbed species. The photo generated electrons are able to migrate to the surface are primarily used in the reduction of O₂ in both aqueous and gaseous solution, other reactive species such as the super oxide radical involving H₂O₂ or O₃³³⁻³⁵.

Role of photogenerated holes in photocatalysis :

The positively charged photogenerated holes which might migrate to the surface can either directly oxidize organic species with lower oxidation potentials or they can create the highly reactive and short lived hydroxyl radical OH[•] upon the catalysts adsorption of H₂O. It is accepted that H₂O is absorbed both molecularly and dissociatively³⁶⁻³⁹.

Effect of various factors on rate of photocatalysis :

Effect of oxygen :

The rates of photocatalytic degradation of organic molecules are significantly improved in the presence of oxygen or by the addition of several inorganic oxidizing species such as peroxydisulphate, periodate and peroxides. Molecular oxygen is primarily as an efficient conduction band electron trap, suppressing electron-hole recombination. Photocatalytic activity is nearly completely suppressed in the absence of oxygen, possibly because of

back interfacial electron transfer from active species present on the photocatalyst surface and the steady-state concentration of oxygen has a profound effect on the relative rate of photo catalyzed decontamination occurring under ambient conditions^{40,41}. Thus the superoxide is found as an effective oxygenation agent attacking both neutral substrates and surface adsorbed radicals and radical ions⁴².

Effect of hydroxyl radical :

Numerous studies have assumed competing roles for the photo generates hydroxyl radicals⁴³⁻⁴⁶ and for the trapping hole⁴⁷ in photocatalysis. A surface bound hydroxyl radical is chemically equivalent to a surface trapped hole. The suppression of photocatalytic reactivity when a substrate is bound tightly to an insulating surface during the illumination of a metal oxide semiconductor when both are suspended in a common aqueous solvent⁴⁸. Hydroxyl radical presence increases uniformly the photocatalytic efficiency of a given oxidative conversion. The oxidative degradation rate might be proportionately enhanced as higher concentrations of hydrogen peroxide were formed during the photocatalysis. Hydrogen peroxide can be competitively reduced by a conduction band electron to give a hydroxyl radical and a hydroxide ion. An enhancement upon adding H₂O₂ was observed in the photocatalytic decomposition of phenol⁴⁹, organo phosphorus derivative⁵⁰ and dioxane⁵¹. H₂O₂HCO₃⁻ and hydroperoxy radical may in fact function as a hydroxyl radical scavenger.

Effect of other ions and metals :

The common inorganic anions affect the rates of photooxidation of organic compound on irradiation. It is suggests that inorganic anion may compete with the organic substrate for surface active sites or can form a highly polar environment near the particle surface, thus blocking the diffusion or organics to the active site. Inclusion of transition metal ion dopants might alter the electron-hole recombination rate and enhance the photo responsiveness of the semiconductor⁵²⁻⁵⁷. Loading of heavy metals induce faster electron-hole pair recombination⁵⁸. Sulfur-containing compounds, OH anions, EDTA, and other chelating agents are known to influence the band edge positions of some semiconductors, shifting the conduction band to a more negative potential⁵⁹.

Adsorption effect :

Metal oxide surfaces have a surface density of about 4-5 hydroxyl groups/nm². These can be grouped into sets of surface hydroxyl groups with varying acidities⁶⁰⁻⁶², as has been shown with a Freundlich isotherm requiring a continuous distribution of adsorption energies⁶³. Many organic substrates can themselves act as adsorbed traps for the photogenerated hole, either directly or through the intermediacy of a surface hydroxyl radical⁶⁴.

Effect of pH :

Photocatalytic reactions occurring on metal oxide or metal chalcogenide semiconductor powders suspended in aqueous solution is the weak dependence of the reaction rate on solution pH⁶⁵⁻⁶⁹. The particle size, surface charge, and band edge positions of semiconductor are strongly influenced by pH⁷⁰. Evidence for the importance of surface charge on substrate adsorptivity and higher reaction rates for various photocatalytic conversions at both low pH or at high pH can be found in the literature. pH effects have also been shown to be significant factors in governing photo reduction and deposition of metals.

Effect of temperature :

The rate of photo assisted decomposition of aliphatic alcohols was insensitive to temperature variation^{71,72}. Arrhenius behavior was observed in the photo detoxification of phenol⁷³ and salicylic acid⁷⁴, although a linear dependence of reaction rate on temperature was reported in the photocatalyzed decomposition of chloroform⁷⁵.

Kinetic study :

Recombination of the photogenerated electron and hole is so fast, interfacial electron transfer is kinetically competitive only when the relevant donor or acceptor is pre adsorbed before photolysis. It is suggested that preliminary adsorption is a prerequisite for highly efficient the detoxification⁷⁶. The substrate pre adsorption on a given photocatalyst can be probed by the use of a Langmuir Hinshelwood kinetic model⁷⁷⁻⁸⁴ modified to accommodate reactions occurring at a solid-liquid interface.

Conclusion

A widely applicable method for activating adsorbed organic molecules is photocatalysis. It is promising as a route to selective synthetic transformation or as an ad-

vanced oxidation process for environmental cleanup. Heterogeneous photocatalysis takes place at ambient temperature and pressure with complete oxidation of substances into CO₂ and H₂O. The oxygen necessary for the heterogeneous photocatalysis is obtained from the atmosphere and the catalyst is cheap, easily available and can be reused. It has no waste disposal problem.

Acknowledgement

The Head of the Department is gratefully acknowledged for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. V. Parmon, A. Emeline and N. Serpone, *Int. J. Photoen.*, 2002, **4**, 91.
2. A. L. Linsebigler, G. Q. Lu and J. T. Yates, *J. Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 735.
3. F. Sabin, T. Tiirk and A. Vogler, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1992, **63**, 99.
4. M. A. Fox and M. T. Dulay, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 341.
5. V. Brezova, S. Vodny, M. Veaely, M. Ceppan and L. Lapcik, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1991, **56**, 125.
6. S. Yamagata, R. Baba and A. Fujishima, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 1004.
7. J. Peral, J. Casado and J. Domenech, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1988, **44**, 209.
8. T. Hisanaga, K. Harada and K. Tanaka, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1990, **56**, 113.
9. R. Borello, C. Minero, E. Pramauro, E. Pelizzetti, N. Serpone and H. Hidaka, *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.*, 1989, **8**, 997.
10. D. M. Blake, "Bibliography of Work on the Photocatalytic Removal of Hazardous Compounds from Water and Air", NREL/TP-430-22197, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Golden Co., 1997.
11. Y. Xu and M. Schoonem, *American Mineralogist*, 2000, **85**, 543.
12. A. Sclafani, L. Palmisano and M. Schiavello, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 828.
13. M. Anpo, K. Chiba, M. Tomonari, S. Coluccia, M. Che and M. A. Fox, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1991, **64**, 543.
14. T. Hayashi, H. Yao, S. Takabara and K. Mi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 2866.
15. P. V. Kamat and M. A. Fox, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1983, **102**, 379.
16. G. T. Brown and J. R. Danvent, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1984, **80**, 1631.
17. C. Arbour, D. K. Sharma and C. H. Langford, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 331.

18. M. A. Fox, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1988, **16**, 314.
19. A. J. Bard, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1979, **83**, 3146.
20. A. J. Bard, *J. Photochem.*, 1979, **10**, 150.
21. A. J. Bard, *Science*, 1980, **207**, 139.
22. A. J. Nozik, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **29**, 189.
23. P. Cooper, *J. Soc. Dyers Col.*, 1993, **109**, 97.
24. N. Shapovalov, E. Stenfanovich and T. Troung, *Surface Science*, 2002, **498**, 103.
25. P. Grau, *Water Sci. Technol.*, 1991, **24**, 97.
26. J. Hao and P. C. Chang, *Crit. Rev. Env. Sci. Tech.*, 2000, **30**, 449.
27. P. V. Kamat, *Langmuir*, 1990, **6**, 512.
28. J. M. Warman, M. P. Dehaas, P. Pichat and N. Serpone, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 8858.
29. G. Rothenberger, J. Moser, M. Gritzel, N. Serpone and D. K. Sharma, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **107**, 8054.
30. J. Abrahame, R. S. Davidson and C. L. Morrison, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1986, **29**, 353.
31. T. Shiragami, C. Pac and S. Yanagida, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 504.
32. C. H. Fwher and M. Giereig, *Langmuir*, 1992, **41**, 475.
33. N. S. Lewis and M. L. Roenbluth, "Photocatalysis", John Wiley and Sons, 1989, 99.
34. J. Bednarek and S. Schlick, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 9940.
35. J. Zheneheng, F. Linagbo, L. Qinglin, W. Chuanping and S. Mengyang, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1991, **70**, 361.
36. D. Lawless, N. Serpone and D. Meieel, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 5166.
37. R. B. Draper and M. A. Fox, *Langmuir*, 1990, **6**, 1396.
38. R. B. Draper and M. A. Fox, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 4628.
39. S. Sato, *Langmuir*, 1988, **4**, 1156.
40. M. A. Fox and C. C. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 6757.
41. H. Gerischer and A. Heller, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1992, **139**, 113.
42. S. F. Nelsen, M. F. Teasely and P. L. Kapp, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 5503.
43. J. Cunningham and S. Srijaranai, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1988, **43**, 329.
44. M. Gritzel and R. F. Howe, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 2566.
45. V. Brezova, A. Staeko and L. Lapcik, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1991, **59**, 115.
46. J. Soria, J. C. Conesa, Y. Auguliaro, L. Palmho, M. Schiavello and A. Sclafani, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 274.
47. R. F. Howe and M. Gritzel, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 3906.
48. C. Minero, F. Catozzo and E. Pelizzetti, *Langmuir*, 1992, **8**, 481.
49. A. Sclafani, L. Palmho and E. Davi, *New. J. Chem.*, 1990, **14**, 265.
50. C. K. Gritzel, M. Jiroueeek and M. Gritzel, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1990, **60**, 375.
51. E. Pelizzetti, V. Carlin, C. Minero and M. Gritzel, *New. J. Chem.*, 1991, **15**, 351.
52. H. Frei, D. J. Fitzmaurice and M. Grlitzel, *Langmuir*, 1990, **6**, 198.
53. J. Kiwi and M. Gritzel, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 637.
54. K. R. Thampi, J. Kiwi and M. Gritzel, *Catal. Lett.*, 1988, **1**, 109.
55. J. B. Goodenough, *Adv. Chem. Ser.*, 1980, **186**, 113.
56. W. K. Wong and M. A. Mnlati, *Sol. Energy*, 1988, **36**, 163.
57. T. R. N. Kutty and K. Avudaithai, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1989, **163**, 93.
58. N. Jaffrezic-Renault, P. Pichat, A. Foissy and R. Mercier, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 2733.
59. T. Uchihara, M. Matsumura, J. Ono and H. Tsubomura, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 415.
60. P. Pichat, M. N. Mozzanega and H. Courbon, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1987, **83**, 697.
61. T. Yamanaka and K. Tanabe, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 2409.
62. K. Kobayakawa, Y. Nakazawa, M. Ikeda, Y. Sato and A. Fujishima, *Ber. Bunsen. Ges. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 1439.
63. S. Tunesi and M. Anderson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 3399.
64. M. A. Fox, C. C. Chen and B. A. Lindig, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 5828.
65. H. Harada, T. Ueda and T. Sakata, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **93**, 1542.
66. J. Sabate, M. A. Anderson, M. A. Aguado, J. Guminez, S. Cervera March and C. G. Hill, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1992, **71**, 57.
67. T. L. Roee and C. Nanjundiah, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **89**, 3766.
68. G. T. Brown and J. R. Darwent, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 4955.
69. O. Enea and A. J. Bard, *Novv. J. Chim.*, 1986, **9**, 281.
70. B. Siffert and J. M. Metzger, *Colloids Surf.*, 1991, **53**, 79.
71. P. Pichat, M. N. Mozzanega, J. Disdier and J. M. Hermman, *Novv. J. Chim.*, 1982, **11**, 559.

72. N. R. Blake and G. L. Griffin, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, **92**, 6697.
73. K. Okamoto, Y. Yamamoto, H. Tanaka and A. Itaya, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1985, **58**, 2023.
74. R. W. Matthew, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 3328.
75. D. Bahnemann, D. Bockelmann and R. Goelich, *Sol. Energy Motor.*, 1991, **24**, 564.
76. R. W. Matthew, *J. Catal.*, 1988, **113**, 549.
77. C. S. Turchi and D. F. Ollie, *J. Catal.*, 1990, **122**, 178.
78. B. Jenny and P. Pichat, *Langmuir*, 1991, **7**, 947.
79. I. Langmuir, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, **17**, 621.
80. R. W. Matthew, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1989, **85**, 1291.
81. J. Cunningham and S. Srijaranai, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1991, **58**, 361.
82. R. W. Matthew, *J. Catal.*, 1988, **111**, 264.
83. C. N. Satterfield, "Heterogeneous Catalysis in Practice", McGraw Hill, New York, 1980, 46.
84. L. K. Doraiswamy and M. M. Sharma, "Heterogeneous Reactions : Analysis, Examples, and Reactor Design" , Wiley, New York, 1984, 17.